

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' CRIMINAL EMOTIONAL-CIVIC COMPETENCES BASED ON THE TECHNOLOGY "DEBATE" IN NATIVE LANGUAGE EDUCATION

Arabboyeva Makhfuzakhon Akramjonovna

Doctoral student of Andijan State Pedagogical Institute

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The purpose of the subject of mother tongue is to form language-related knowledge, skills and competencies in the student, to form logical, critical, and creative thinking skills, to develop students' speech culture and communication skills, at the same time, to form spiritual and moral qualities such as national pride, patriotism, humanity, correctness, and honesty, to equip them with the skills of adhering to literary and moral standards, to develop social, emotional, and civic competencies in students and, through this, to understand their place in society and civic duty, to form competencies such as a critical approach to problematic situations, to develop skills aimed at turning students into active participants in social life, to help students become mature individuals, that is, to form qualities such as independent thinking, self-management, and setting life plans in them, to take into account their individual characteristics, abilities, needs, and interests, and to provide them with the necessary support for their individual development. Achieving the goal of today's native language education is a priority in the teaching of the native language.

The correct selection and application of various modern pedagogical technologies and methods in the educational process in fulfilling the goals and objectives of the native language is important for today's education. We would like to propose the use of the "Debate" technology in the development of students' social-emotional-civic competencies.

Description of the technology: This technology serves to form social-emotional and civic competencies in students by developing skills and competencies such as independent and creative thinking, the ability to freely express personal thoughts and opinions, the ability to critically and analytically assess the situation, decision-making, teamwork, and respect the opinions of their teammates, as well as a culture of debate.

When a lesson is organized based on this technology, students are divided into small groups and tasks are completed individually and collaboratively.

The purpose of technology: To help students take their place in society, actively participate in the life of the state and society, to develop leadership qualities, teamwork skills, independent and creative thinking, the ability to freely express personal thoughts and opinions, critical and analytical assessment

of the situation, decision-making, teamwork, respect for the opinions of teammates, and the formation of a culture of debate, thereby forming and developing social emotional and civic competencies in students.

Application of technology: Can be used in native language lessons and extracurricular educational hours. Technology-based educational sessions are organized in classrooms based on dividing students into groups.

Tools used in the session: Whatman paper, A4 white sheets of paper, colored felt-tip pens, markers and glue.

The procedure for conducting the lesson:

- Before starting the lesson, the teacher introduces the students to the requirements for conducting a discussion and the step-by-step procedure for conducting the lesson.

- The teacher divides the students into groups based on certain criteria.

- Each group begins to work on the requirements and tasks set for their problem and its solution.

- A discussion begins between the groups on the topic or existing problem.

Organizing a lesson based on technology:

Stage 1: The teacher begins the lesson by announcing discussion questions. For example, What is a culture of communication? How can a person achieve a culture of speech? Is it important for a person to have a culture of speech in order to take his place in society? Is a citizen of a state obliged to know the state language? Can a person live in society without communication? The questions are digitized and the group participants choose questions through closed numbers at their own discretion. The teacher sets a time to prepare for the discussion. Each participant of each group must write his personal opinion on the questions selected for the discussion on the Whatman paper distributed to the groups, sign his name and surname under the idea, and pay attention to the correct construction of the sentence in each written idea, spelling and grammar rules.

Stage 2: Each group prepares the necessary materials using tracing paper, A4 white paper, colored markers, markers and glue based on the questions they have chosen. One person from the group members is selected by the group members to present the prepared materials.

Stage 3: When the groups are ready for the discussion within the allotted time, each group is given a turn to present and the presentation time is set. The group representative speaks on behalf of his or her team and expresses his or her opinions based on the materials and evidence prepared on the given topic

within the allotted time. Group members can add to the opinions expressed. While one group is presenting, other groups should listen carefully and respectfully to the opinions of the presenting group and prepare 1 important question for the group based on the presentation.

Stage 4: After everyone has presented, the groups take turns asking each other the questions they prepared during the presentation. The remaining groups take turns asking questions to the group that made the first presentation, and there is no time set for preparing to answer. This process is repeated in each group.

Step 5: After listening to the presentations and answers of each group, the teacher quickly collects the Whatmans and checks the written thoughts in terms of style, grammar and spelling.

Step 6: Summarizes the thoughts expressed by the groups and expresses his/her opinions on these topics. Answers the questions asked by the groups.

At the end of the lesson, the teacher analyzes the activities of each group during the training process, thanks them and concludes the training.

In conclusion, organizing educational processes on the basis of modern pedagogical technologies helps to easily develop the knowledge, skills, qualifications and competencies that a student should acquire through quality educational processes. Properly selected educational technology creates the opportunity to fulfill the requirements, goals and tasks of education in a holistic manner.

References:

1. “O‘zbekistonning yangi taraqqiyot davrida ta’lim-tarbiya va ilm-fan sohalarini rivojlantirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida”gi O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 06.11.2020-yildagi PF-6108-son farmoni.
2. “2022 — 2026-yillarda xalq ta’limini rivojlantirish bo‘yicha milliy dasturni tasdiqlash to‘g‘risida” 11.05.2022. PF-133-son farmoni.
3. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2017-yil 6-apreldagi “Umumiy o‘rta va o‘rta maxsus, kasb-hunar ta’limining davlat ta’lim standartlarini tasdiqlash to‘g‘risida” gi 187-son qarori.
4. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2017-yil 6-apreldagi “Umumiy o‘rta va o‘rta maxsus, kasb-hunar ta’limining davlat ta’lim standartlarini tasdiqlash to‘g‘risida” gi 187-son qarori asosida yaratilgan Ona tili fanidan o‘quv dasturi (5-9-sinf)
5. Ona tili fani bo‘yicha O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Uzluksiz ta’lim milliy o‘quv dasturlari. Ta’lim sifatini nazorat qilish davlat inspeksiyasi. Toshkent-2021.

6. Incheon declaration/ Education 2030: Towards inclusive and equitable quality education and lifelong learning for all (Word Education Forum, 19-22 may 2015, Incheon, Republic of Korea).- Корея.-2015. 35-bet.
7. Arabboyeva M.A. Ona tili darslari orqali o'quvchilarning ijtimoiy-emotsional-fuqarolik kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish. *Замонавий таълим / современное образование*. 2022, 12-son. 43-47-betlar.
8. Arabboyeva M.A. Ona tili darslarini milliy dastur talablari asosida tashkil etish dolzarb pedagogik muammo sifatida. *Scientific Bulletin of NamSU-Научный вестник НамГУ-NamDU ilmiy axborotnomasi – 2023 - yil, 7-son*.
9. Arabboyeva M.A. O'quvchilarda ijtimoiy-emotsional-fuqarolik kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishning psixologik-pedagogik xususiyatlari. *Замонавий таълим / современное образование*. 2024.№5(138), 47-52-betlar.
10. Arabboyeva M.A. O'quvchilarning ijtimoiy emotsional-fuqarolik kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish. "Umumiy filologiyaning dolzarb masalalari" mavzusidagi Respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya materiallari, Andijon. 2023-yil, 14-iyun, 137-142.
11. Arabboyeva M.A. Ona tili darslarida ijtimoiy emotsional – fuqarolik kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishga qo'yiladigan didaktik talablar. Andijon davlat chet tillari instituti hamda –UNIVERSAL xalqaro ilmiy jurnali hamkorligida "Globallashuv jarayonida fan va ta'lim muammolari va yechimlari" mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya materiallari. 2024-yil 5-iyun, 224-227.
12. Arabboyeva M.A. Pedagogical-psychological and methodological features of developing social-emotional-civic competence in mother language lessons. *INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY*, 2025. (T. 5, Выпуск 3, сс. 71–78). Zenodo.